

Retrograde Ureteroscopy with Pneumatic Lithotripsy in the Treatment of Proximal Ureteric Stones: A Retrospective Analysis of Outcomes and Complications

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ABSTRACT

Background: Proximal ureteric stones present peculiar management challenges. **Objective:** This study seeks to audit the outcomes and complications of using semirigid ureteroscopy with pneumatic lithotripsy for the treatment of proximal ureteric stones. **Methodology:** The records of 18 patients who had semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy for proximal ureteric stone over a period of 2 years were reviewed. All the patients had computed tomography (CT) abdominal scan to characterize the stones before the surgery. Data on patients' demographics, stone location, stone size, intraoperative complications, postoperative complications, and stone clearance were retrieved and analysed using proportions, frequency and percentages. **Results:** The mean age of the patients in years was 44.17 ± 12.32 (range 29–67). The mean stone size was 15.01 ± 4.51 mm with range of 8.3mm–22.0mm. All the patients had impacted stones. Out of the 18 patients, 6 (33.3%), 11 (61.1%) and 1 (5.6%) had grade II, grade III and grade IV hydronephrosis respectively. Three (16.7%) patients had mucosal flap, 6 (33.3%) had mucosal abrasion, 2 (11.1%) patients had transient haematuria postoperatively while 1 (5.6%) patient had UTI. Successful disintegration and retrieval of stone fragments occurred in 12 (66.7%) patients. In 4 (22.2%) patients, stone/stone fragments retropulsed into the pelvicalyceal system and the procedure had to be completed with flexible ureteroscopy. In another 2 (11.1%) patients, the procedure was converted to open ureterolithotomy due to oedema and inflammatory polyps, tortuosity of the ureter precluding stone visualization, and stone fragmentation. **Conclusion:** Treatment of proximal ureteric stones with semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy gives acceptable stone free rate with minimal complications. But complementary ancillary procedures, particularly flexible ureteroscopy should be anticipated to achieve a higher stone clearance rate.

Keywords: Ureteroscopy, Pneumatic lithotripsy, Proximal ureteric stone

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INTRODUCTION

Urinary stone is a widespread disease with a high rate of morbidity.¹ It constitutes a significant burden to the health service and consumes a huge chunk of healthcare resources.^{2,3} Proximal ureteric stones present peculiar treatment challenges. The patient's weight, anatomical anomalies, stone size, stone density, surgeon's experience as well as availability of equipment may inform the choice of treatment strategy.⁴ Contemporarily, these treatment options include extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL), ureteroscopy (URS), laparoscopic ureterolithotomy, open ureterolithotomy and antegrade (PCNL).^{5,6} Extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy has been the preferred treatment modality for the proximal ureteric stones.⁷ However, in stones more than 1cm and in impacted stones, ESWL becomes a less efficient and costly tool requiring many sessions to achieve acceptable stone clearance rate. The decreased efficacy of the ESWL for impacted stone is well documented.⁸

Percutaneous nephrolithotomy has been suggested in such scenarios, but is associated with unacceptable complications rate even in expert hands.⁹ Laparoscopic ureterolithotomy and open ureterolithotomy also are more invasive with the need for longer hospital stay.¹⁰

Ureteroscopy (URS) has been conventionally reserved for mid and distal ureteric stones.^{11,12} With the development of smaller calibre semirigid and flexible ureteroscopes, URS has become a safer and more effective modality in the treatment of proximal ureteric stones.¹³

While holmium: YAG laser is the most commonly used energy source in the fragmentation of urinary stones in the developed countries,¹⁴ it is expensive in our subregion. Pneumatic lithotripter is strong enough for fragmenting all types of stones, has little damage to the ureteric mucosa and therefore an ideal fragmentation energy for stones in the ureter.¹⁵

This study seeks to audit the outcomes and complications of the use of semirigid ureteroscopy with pneumatic lithotripsy in the management of proximal ureteric stones.

METHODOLOGY

Design and Setting of Study

This is a hospital-based retrospective case series carried out between April, 2020 and May, 2022. The records of 18 patients who underwent semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy for proximal ureteric stones were reviewed. The study was carried out at a Multi-specialty Hospital in Jos, North-central Nigeria.

Participants and Data Collection

All the patients had preoperative evaluation and sterile urine culture was ensured. They also had serum electrolytes, urea, and creatinine. All patients had abdominal computed tomography (CT) scan before the surgery to locate the stone, determine its size and study the anatomy of the ureter and the pelvicalyceal system.

Stone size was measured using the longest axis of the stone viewed on the coronary plane of the CT scan.

Hydronephrosis was graded as: Grade I (Mild)-Renal pelvis dilatation; Grade II (Moderate)-Major calyceal dilatation; Grade III (Moderate)-Minor calyceal dilatation; Grade IV (Severe)-Cortical thinning. Stone was considered to be impacted in the study if it gave rise to moderate (Grade II and Grade III) to severe (Grade IV) hydronephrosis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Proximal ureteric stone was defined as calculus located between the superior margin of the sacroiliac joint and the pelvic-ureteric junction. Patients who had semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy for stones located in the proximal ureter were included.

Patients that had ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy for ureteric stones located below the upper margin of the sacroiliac joint were excluded from the analysis. Also, patients in whom there was failure to access the ureter retrogradely were not included in the review.

Statistical Analysis

Relevant patients' demographics, indication for the surgery, location of the stone, size of stone, preoperative double J (DJ) placement, postoperative DJ stent placement, intraoperative ureteric dilatation, intraoperative complications, postoperative complications, duration of surgery, and duration of hospital stay as well as stone clearance were obtained. The data were entered into and analysed using SPSS® version 22 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, New York, US) for proportions, frequency and percentages.

Permission for the study was obtained from Research and Ethical Committee. Informed consent was obtained for the patients who fulfilled the criteria for inclusion in the study.

Surgical technique

The ureteroscopy was carried out under general anaesthesia (GA) with muscle relaxation. The patient was placed in lithotomy position and cystoscopy was carried out to assess the lower urinary tract and to gain retrograde access to the ureter with cannulation of ureteric orifice with a 5Fr ureteric catheter. Retrograde pyelogram was then performed using Ultravist-300 in 1:1 dilution to outline the anatomy of the ureter and the pelvicalyceal system. A size 0.035inch guide wire (Microinvasive, Boston Scientific Corp, USA) was placed. A new hydrophilic guidewire (Terumo Medical Corporation, Japan) was used for each case to facilitate navigation across the impacted stone. Gentle and rotating movements was required in most cases to get the guidewire to pass across to the pelvicalyceal system. In some cases, we placed DJ stent preoperatively for 2 - 4 weeks, mainly to facilitate access to the stone. Ureteroscopy was then carried out using size

6.0/7.5Fr semirigid ureteroscope (Richard Wolf, Knittlingen, Germany). Stones were fragmented using 0.8mm pneumatic lithotripter probe (Lithomed) set at 8-12Hz in multi-pulse mode. The fragments were removed using a triprong forceps. Irrigation was achieved with normal saline using a hand-controlled pressure bag to achieve a clear vision. A size 10FR size feeding tube was inserted into the bladder to keep it empty and reduce the pressure in the upper urinary tract. In all patients, C-arm (Philips, Netherlands) was used to guide the essential steps of the procedure where necessary, particularly guide wire insertion, some steps of ureteroscope manipulations and insertion of DJ stents. The principle of ALARA (as low as reasonably achievable) was strictly followed and all theatre personnel were adequately protected by wearing lead aprons and thyroid shields.

Anti-retropulsion device was not used in any of the patients. Double J stent was placed in all our patients postoperatively since they all had impacted stones.

Foley catheter left in place to rest the bladder was removed on the first day after the operation before the patient was discharged home. Intravenous antibiotics were given for 24hours postoperative and subsequently oral antibiotics were administered. Double J (DJ) was removed at 4 weeks. Postoperative analgesia consisted mainly of oral paracetamol.

Most patients were discharged home on postoperative day 1. At follow-up in 4 weeks and at 6 months, radiological investigations were tailored to post-operative clinical evaluation of the patients and included plain abdominal x-ray and CT urography. Success of the procedure was defined as satisfactory disintegration and retrieval of the stone with the semirigid ureteroscope without need for flexible ureteroscopy or conversion to open ureterolithotomy. Perioperative complications including ureteric mucosal flap, mucosal abrasion and bleeding, ureteral perforation and urinary tract infection were observed for in the patients.

RESULTS

A total of eighteen patients had ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy for stones located in the proximal ureter. Of the 18 patients, 13 (72.2%) were males while 5 (27.8%) were females giving a male to female ratio of M: F = 2.6: 1. The mean age of the patients was 44.17±12.32 (range 29 - 67) years.

The mean stone size was 15.01±4.51mm with range of 8.30mm–22.00mm. All the stones were impacted in the proximal ureter. Other stone characteristics are as shown in Table 1

Table 1. Patients and Stone Characteristics

Characteristic	n (%)
Hydronephrosis	
Grade II	6(33.3%)
Grade III	11(61.1%)
Grade IV	1 (5.6%)
Laterality	
Right	10(55.6%)
Left	8(44.4%)
Stone size	
≤1cm	3(16.7%)
>1cm	15(83.3%)
Preoperative DJ stenting	
Yes	9(50%)
No	9(50%)
Retropulsion	
Yes	4(22.2%)
No	14(77.8%)

Nine (50.0%) patients had DJ stent placed preoperatively and 9 (50.0%) patients did not have preoperative DJ stents. Also following the ureteroscopy, DJ stent was placed in all the patients postoperatively.

All the patients had general anaesthesia. The mean intraoperative time was 89mins (range 30 - 193min). Longer intraoperative time was spent on patients who had conversion to either flexible ureteroscopy or open ureterolithotomy. All the patients in this study were presenting for the first time with their stone disease. None had previous intervention like open ureterolithotomy, ureteroscopy or ESWL.

Successful disintegration and retrieval of stone fragments occurred in 12(66.7%) patients. In 4(22.2%) patients, stone/stone fragments retropulsed into the pelvicalyceal system and the procedure had to be completed with flexible ureteroscopy. So, in total, 16 (88.9%) patients the stones were successfully treated with semirigid ureteroscopy/pneumatic lithotripsy first and where necessary flexible ureteroscopy/holmium: YAG laser lithotripsy. In another 2 (11.1%) patients the procedure had to be converted to open ureterolithotomy due to florid oedema and inflammatory polyps, as well as tortuosity of the ureter precluding stone visualization and efficient fragmentation of the stone.

The complications observed during the surgery and during follow up visits at four (4) weeks and at six (6) months are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Complications observed in the 18 patients that had semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy

Perioperative complications	n (%)
Intraoperative complications	
Mucosal flap	3(16.7%)
Mucosal abrasion	6(33.3%)
Avulsion	0
Bleeding	2(11.1%)
Ureteral perforation	1(5.6%)
Postoperative complications	
Haematuria	2(11.1%)
UTI	1(5.6%)

DISCUSSION

In this study, the success rate was 66.7%. Many authors achieved similar success rate.^{11,16,17} Specifically, Yencilek and colleagues in Istanbul and Galal and colleagues in Egypt, in their experience achieved success rate of 71.7% and 66.0% respectively.^{11,16} Elhanainy and colleagues also in Egypt on the other hand reported a success rate of 91% and concluded that the use of semirigid URS and pneumatic lithotripsy is very satisfactory in the treatment of proximal ureteric stone.¹⁷ While this isolated high success rate may

not be spurious, very high success rate is not easily replicated in many series even in high volume centres.^{11,16,17}

Generally, semirigid and pneumatic lithotripsy has a lower success rate for proximal ureteric stones compared to stones in the mid and distal ureter. The lower success rate is attributed principally to retropulsion of the proximal stones to the pelvicalyceal system (PCS).^{11,18} In this study, 4(22.2%) patients had their stone migrated to the PCS and accounted for most of the failure rate we observed. Retropulsion easily happens due to dilatation of the ureter proximal to the stone, strong irrigation fluid pressure, impulsion power from the lithotripter and shorter distance to the kidney.¹¹

We used pneumatic lithotripter for stone disintegration. It is a good stone disintegration for stones with high Hounsfield units. The unfavourable aspect of the lithotripter is higher incidence of stone retropulsion, requiring meticulous and experienced approach to overcome.¹⁹ However, pneumatic lithotripter has an advantage of fragmenting stones without causing bleeding from mucosal injury thereby maintaining a clear operation field, particularly in the setting of impacted stones.¹⁵ While holmium:YAG laser lithotripter is also useful in this setting, retropulsion though reduced can still occur.¹⁴ With laser, mucosal injury, bleeding and ureteral perforation are frequent complications, and careful lithotripsy without touching the oedematous and polypous ureteral wall in impacted stone scenario sometimes can be difficult.²⁰

In this series, lithotripsy was completed with flexible ureteroscopy when there was retropulsion into the PCS. Turkan and colleagues recommend that flexible ureteroscopy should be considered as complementary to, rather than an alternative to semirigid ureteroscopy in the endoscopic treatment of proximal ureteric stone.²¹ In our opinion, this is a more reasonable and cost-effective approach than to use the expensive

flexible ureteroscope/laser fibre for every case of proximal ureteric stone.

Two (11.1%) of our patients had open ureterolithotomy due to lack of visualization of the ureteric stone at both semirigid and flexible ureteroscopy. This difficulty was caused by severe tortuosity of the ureter in one case and severe fibrosis in the other. While open or laparoscopic ureterolithotomy is an acceptable management strategy for proximal ureteric stones, they are more invasive. Therefore, they should be preserved for patients who have large and severely impacted stones in whom all endoscopic manipulations fail.^{5,6}

All (100%) the patients in this study had impacted stones giving rise to varying degree of hydronephrosis. Impacted proximal ureteric stone progressively leads to hydronephrosis resulting in partial or complete loss of renal function if prompt treatment is not instituted.²² Also, when ureteric stone is impacted, it presents a peculiar and challenging situation at ureteroscopy due to oedema of the ureteral wall, inflammatory polyps and sometimes fibrous stenosis at the stone site,²³ The oedema and fibrosis are thought to be due to ischaemia from chronic pressure by the stone or from immunological reaction to the stone material.²³ During ureteroscopy, the difficulty and in many instances, the inability to pass a guide wire across the impacted stone, reduces the safety margin and increases the possibility of complications.¹⁰

A spectrum of partial and full thickness ureteric wall injuries could occur during ureteroscopy. Mucosal abrasion results from shearing forces against the luminal ureteral layer from either ureteroscope or from extraction of stone.²⁴ We observed this complication in 6(33.3%) of our patients. This was managed by DJ stent placement which we, in any case, inserted for all patients in index series. The placement of DJ stent, particularly after lithotripsy for impacted stones relieves ureteric wall oedema, enhances easy

passage of stone fragments and may reduce the incidence of ureteric stricture formation.²⁵

We encountered mucosal flap in 3(16.7%) of our patients. In those cases, the procedure was quickly completed and DJ stent inserted. Mucosal flap or false passage may occur while introducing guidewire, ureteroscope or different working instruments. Gealvelete and colleagues recorded this complication in 2.8% of their patients.²⁶

Ureteric perforation is a full thickness injury through the ureteral wall. Generally, there has been a lower incidence of ureteric perforation in the contemporary practice [27]. In this series we recorded 1(5.6%) case of ureteric perforation. The risk increases in the setting of severely oedematous ureteric wall in impacted stone scenario.²³

We did not encounter a case of ureteric stricture as the follow up period was short. Impacted stone, particularly those with extended period of time is a high-risk factor for ureteric stricture formation.^{28,29} Deliveliotis and colleagues in their study on management and follow up of impacted ureteric stones, found that in 30 patients of their patients, 2(6%) developed ureteric stricture as a long-term complication.³⁰

This study is not without limitations. For instance, the small number of patients and the relatively short duration of follow up of patients constitute limitations in this study. Also, our data represent a retrospective review and therefore subject to inherent biases of retrospective study.

CONCLUSION

Treatment of proximal ureteric stones with semirigid ureteroscopy and pneumatic lithotripsy gives acceptable stone free rate with minimal complications. But complementary ancillary procedures, particularly flexible ureteroscopy should be anticipated to achieve a higher stone clearance rate.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Financial support for the article: Nil

Authors' contributions

Akpayak conceived, designed the study; acquired, analysed and interpreted the data as well as wrote the draft of the manuscript. Adedeji contributed to the acquisition, analysis and interpretation of data. Umana analysed and interpreted the data. All the authors revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content and approved the final version that is submitted.

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